

THE DISPERSION AND STABILITY OF GRAPHENE OXIDE IN POLYSTYRENE

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ABSTRACT

Graphene materials are exciting candidates as fillers in polymer composites because of their superb physical properties that it is hoped can be transferred to the polymer. Here we study the dispersion of graphene oxide (GO) within polystyrene, and its stability during processing. The solution processed composite results in GO which is initially well exfoliated and dispersed within the polymer. Rheology shows that at 0.48% vol GO a percolated network is formed, which also interacts with the polymer, reducing the plateau modulus in melt conditions. Despite being well dispersed, under further thermal annealing the GO is seen to aggregate within the composite by small-angle X-ray scattering and rheometry. As the ability to maintain a good dispersion of the graphene is vital to unlock improvements in the physical properties of the composite, these results offer an important insight into the stability of GO within a PS matrix, and offer directions for further work compatibilising and stabilising the nanocomposite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene and its related functionalized materials have gained a great deal of attention in recent years in the field of polymer nanocomposites^[1-3], because of the excellent physical properties of the graphene. These properties include superb mechanical strength and excellent thermal and electrical conductivity, which may in turn enhance the properties of the polymer, delivering improved performance and new functionality.

Another key attribute of graphene is its high aspect ratio and specific surface area, holding the potential to deliver the promised composite improvements at much lower loadings compared to other filler materials. Key to achieving these gains is the ability to control, and maintain, a good quality dispersion of the graphene within the composite. The layering of graphene sheets is known to impair the physical properties of the graphene, while percolation of the graphene within the composite is also vital for properties such as electrical and thermal conductivity.

Graphene oxide (GO) is a highly functionalized form of graphene. The functionalities of GO comprise epoxy, hydroxyl, carbonyl and alcohol groups^[4] which can aid dispersion within a polymer matrix, but also offer a convenient, scalable route to a more graphene-like material, reduced graphene oxide (rGO). The functional groups of GO also provide an opportunity for further covalent modification of the surface chemistry of the graphene sheet, to tailor the chemical compatibility to the desired matrix.

Here we study the dispersion and stability of graphene oxide in polystyrene (PS) nanocomposites. By combining several experimental techniques such as small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) and rheometry, we have been able to study the dispersion, percolation and structure of the GO within the composite. This helps us to understand the interaction between PS and GO, and assess the viability of GO as a filler material for PS. These studies will also help guide us on further strategies for the compatibilisation of PS with graphene, with the goal of unlocking the sought after properties of the polymer nanocomposite.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 GRAPHITE OXIDE PREPARATION

Graphite oxide, as the precursor material to graphene oxide, was produced by the Hummers method^[5]. Briefly sulfuric acid (230 mL, 98%) was cooled to 0°C with efficient overhead stirring. To this, graphite (10 g) and sodium nitrate (5 g) was added. Potassium permanganate (30 g) was then added slowly over several hours maintaining a temperature of <10°C. The mixture was then heated to 35°C for 30 min, after which high purity water (460 mL) was added rapidly. The resulting exotherm brought the reaction to approx. 90°C which was maintained for 15 min, after which the reaction was allowed to cool to room temperature. The reaction mix was then poured into high purity water (1400 mL) and hydrogen peroxide (37%, 10 mL). The resulting suspension was allowed to sediment (18 h) and the liquid decanted off. The powder was then collected and successively washed with high purity water by centrifugation (8000 rpm, 20 min) until a pH neutral dark brown slurry was obtained. Graphite oxide was then isolated by freeze-drying.

2.2 COMPOSITE PREPARATION

Samples were prepared by solvent processing in DMF. Briefly the appropriate amount of polymer was weighed. DMF was then added to a final concentration of 10%w/v polymer. To this the appropriate amount of graphite oxide, as the precursor material to graphene oxide, was added and the sample transferred to a roller for 18 h. The sample was then sonicated with a solid probe sonicator (225 W, 20 minutes, 5 second pulses, Cole Parmer 750), causing both the exfoliation of the graphite oxide to graphene oxide (GO), and the mixing of the resulting GO with the polymer. Sonication was done on not more than 50 mL of the dispersion at a time. The polymer-graphene oxide solution was then immediately precipitated dropwise into methanol (10 volume excess to DMF). The resulting precipitate was stirred in methanol (30 minutes), isolated by filtration, and stirred in fresh methanol (18 h), then isolated by filtration. The resulting tan coloured powder was then dried in vacuo (50°C, 18 h).

The composite powder was compressed at room temperature in a press at 9 tons to increase the density, before being hot-pressed into circular moulds at 160°C under a load of 6 tons for 30 minutes unless otherwise stated. The resulting disc-shaped samples were cooled to room temperature and used as prepared.

2.3 RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

Graphene oxide was placed on a glass slide and the Raman spectrum recorded using a 532 nm laser with a Horiba LabRam Evolution. The spectra were collected through an x50 long working distance lens over 5 seconds and averaged over 10 acquisitions. The resulting spectrum was processed to normalize the intensity relative to the most intense peak. The instrument was calibrated using a silicon wafer control.

2.4 X-RAY DIFFRACTION (XRD)

Powdered PS + 0.48 vol% GO composite was loaded on to a glass slide coated in Vaseline and subjected to XRD $2\theta = 5$ and 50° . Measurements were taken with a Bruker AXS d8 Advance X-ray powder automated diffractometers operated at 40 kV and 40 mA, with flat-plane geometry, and using a Cu $K\alpha_{1,2}$ X-ray source ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$).

2.5 THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS (TGA)

Graphene oxide was weighed in to a platinum pan and heated from 30 to 900°C under a flow of compressed air heated at $10^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Chromatographs were collected on a Perkin Elmer Pyris 1 TGA.

2.6 OPTICAL MICROSCOPY

A thin film of PS-GO 0.48 vol% composite (approximately $200 \mu\text{m}$ measured with calipers) was placed on a thermal stage and observed under a transmission microscope (x50 lens). The sample was then heated to 180°C and images recorded overtime under a fixed illumination.

2.7 SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (SEM)

Graphite oxide was exfoliated by sonication, as previously described, in DMF at a concentration of 1 mg mL^{-1} . The sample was then diluted to 0.1 mg mL^{-1} and deposited on a cleaned silicon wafer by dipping the silicon into the DMF solution then allowing it to air dry. The sample was then mounted for SEM and imaged acquired on a Hitachi SU70.

2.8 RHEOMETRY

Oscillatory rheology was carried out using a Thermal Analysis AR2000 rheometer equipped with an Environmental Test Chamber (ETC) under a nitrogen atmosphere. A 25 mm parallel plate geometry was used, and samples tested at a constant strain of 1%, within the linear viscoelastic region. Frequency sweeps were conducted in the range of $0.1\text{-}600 \text{ rad s}^{-1}$ at a temperature of 200°C . The test was then repeated at 10 degree increments down to a final temperature of 140°C . The time temperature superposition (TTS) theory of Williams-Landel-Ferry^[6] was then applied using the RepTate program^[7]. The plateau modulus of the composite samples was determined by taking the value of the storage modulus, G' , at the minimum of the phase shift angle, δ , within the plateau region of the viscoelastic spectrum.

2.9 SAXS

Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) measurements were taken using a Bruker Nanostar instrument (Department of Chemistry, University of Sheffield). Samples were illuminated with a collimated beam X-rays emitted from a Cu- $k(\alpha)$ source and the resulting scattering patterns were collected on a 2D detector. The images were corrected for transmission and background and integrated radially to give data in the form of intensity vs. q . The pure polymer scatter was subtracted to reveal the scattering contribution of the graphene oxide network.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Graphene oxide is an established route to large, batch, quantities of functionalized graphene^[8]. The process involves the oxidation of graphite according to the Hummers method^[5]. The resulting graphite oxide can then be subsequently exfoliated by ultra-sonication to produce single to few layer GO sheets

which are heavily functionalized with oxygen moieties and are polar. The functionalization of graphene is widely used to improve the dispersion and interaction of graphene with a polymer matrix^[9–11]. The dispersion of graphene oxide into a polymer is most easily achieved by the solvent processing method. Here the GO is dispersed into a polymer dissolved in a solvent before subsequently co-precipitating the GO and polymer together into a non-solvent.

Figure 1: (A) SEM image of graphite oxide. Lateral dimensions are in the range of 0.5 to 10 microns, (B) Raman spectrum of graphite oxide, (C) X-ray diffraction of graphite oxide and a 0.48 vol% graphene oxide composite. The disappearance of the graphite interlayer d₀₀₂ peak at $2\theta \approx 12^\circ$ in the composite demonstrates that the graphite oxide is efficiently exfoliated during incorporation into the polymer.

The first step was to confirm that graphite oxide can be successfully exfoliated in DMF. It was found that after sonication a thin material was observed by both scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Figure 1 (A)) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) with lateral dimensions of $< 10 \mu\text{m}$. Raman spectroscopy confirmed that the material retained the chemical structure of graphene oxide (Figure 1 (B))^[12], as seen by the D and G bands (~ 1354 and $\sim 1586 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively) and their relative

intensities. As the dispersion of GO into the polymer solution generally requires sonication it was decided to combine the exfoliation and dispersion steps. Successful exfoliation in the presence of the polymer was confirmed by X-ray diffraction (Figure 1 C)). The presence of the d_{002} peak at $2\theta \approx 12^\circ$ for the graphite oxide shows an interlayer spacing of $\sim 7.9 \text{ \AA}$ between sheets. The absence of this peak in the composite indicates that the stacked graphite oxide sheet structure has been disrupted and the sheets separated, indicating the successful exfoliation to GO within the composite.

Figure 2: Thermogravimetric analysis of graphene oxide in air

It is well known that the thermal treatment of GO can lead to its reduction to reduced graphene oxide (rGO)^[13]. rGO has properties closer to that of graphene compared to GO, with improved thermal and electrical conductivity^[4]. However, the reduction, i.e. the removal of the GO functional groups, also reduces its ability to be dispersed in solvents and polymer matrices^[9]. In order to take advantage of the superior dispersability of GO and the superior conductivity properties of rGO there has been research in to *in situ* thermal reduction methods^[13]. The concept of this method is to use the elevated temperatures involved in the melt processing of polymers to effect a reduction in the GO during the polymer processing. While we have no direct evidence for *in situ* reduction by our process the GO is observed to lose mass when heated above 120°C (Figure 2), well below the process temperatures used in preparing the composites (160°C). The mass losses in the GO sample can be separated into unique events namely loss of adsorbed water, loss of oxygen moieties (reduction)^[14], and finally combustion at 30-100°C, 100-300°C and 400-700°C respectively. Optical microscopy was used to visualize the dispersion of the GO within the composite, during annealing (Figure 3 (A-D)). A progressive darkening of the polymer composite can be observed, with all optical transparency lost after 75 minutes. This is likely to be because of a chemical change in the graphene, such as reduction, so in interpreting the results it must be remembered that the system is dynamic with several processes operating at the same time.

Figure 3: Optical microscopy of a PS + 0.48 vol% GO film heated at 180°C for (A) 0, (B) 30, (C) 60 and (D) 75 minutes, under a $\times 50$ objective lens. Scale bar represents 200 μm .

Rheometry was used to study the viscoelastic properties of the pure polymer, and any changes that occurred upon addition of the GO. Figure 4 shows rheological frequency (ω) sweep data of pure polystyrene (PS) and a composite of the PS with 0.48 vol% graphene oxide (GO). The data was shifted to a single temperature of 200°C by TTS using the RepTate program^[7], allowing us to study the frequency behaviour across a number of decades. This works using the theory of Williams-Landel-Ferry^[6]:

$$\omega(T_0) = a_T \omega(T) \quad (1)$$

where T_0 is the reference temperature and a_T given by:

$$\log a_T = \frac{-C_1(T - T_0)}{T + C_2} \quad (2)$$

with C_1 and C_2 material parameters. C_1 is temperature dependent and varies as

$$C_1^{new} := C_1^{old} \frac{(T_0^{old} + C_2)}{(T_0^{new} + C_2)} \quad (3)$$

A vertical shift for the storage modulus, G' , and loss modulus, G'' , is used to account for changes in density of the polymer with temperature, and is given as follows:

$$G(T_0) = \frac{G(T)}{b_T} \quad (4)$$

and:

$$b_T = \frac{(\rho_0 - TC_3 \cdot 10^{-3})(T + 273.15)}{(\rho_0 - T_0C_3 \cdot 10^{-3})(T_0 + 273.15)} \quad (5)$$

where ρ_0 equals the density of the polymer at 0°C, and the temperature is given in °C.

Figure 4: Oscillatory rheology showing G' (●), G'' (○) and the phase angle δ (◇) of pure PS and PS-0.48 vol% GO nanocomposite as a function of frequency at temperatures of 200-140°C, and a strain of 1%, subject to TTS at a reference temperature of 200°C.

There are two distinct differences apparent in the behaviour of the pure polymer and the composite. At the lowest frequencies it can be seen that there is a levelling in G' of the composite compared to that of the pure polymer. This is also reflected in the downturn of the phase angle, δ , in this region. This indicates an increasing resistance to flow of the polymer caused by the presence of GO within the composite, and percolation of the GO.

The second difference is the notable drop in moduli of the composite compared to that of the pure polymer. The value of the plateau modulus of the polymer, G_N^0 (taken as G' at the minimum of δ) (Figure 4), falls from a value of 150,000 Pa at 0% GO, to 86,600 Pa at 0.48 vol% GO. This reduction in the plateau modulus would make the processing of the composite easier when compared to that of the pure polymer.

The drop in G_N^0 of the PS at 0.48% GO also shows that there is indeed some interaction between the GO and PS, despite the apparent chemical incompatibility of the two materials. It would be expected that the hydrophilic groups of the GO would interact poorly with the hydrophobic PS. However, as discussed previously, it is possible that the GO within the composite has reduced during the thermal processing of the sample, to leave both a hydrophobic rGO and polymer. One way of determining the compatibility of the two materials is to study the stability of the GO in the matrix under annealing. It is possible to look at the GO structure within the matrix by SAXS, as the GO offers contrast to the scattering of the polymer.

Figure 5: Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) data for PS + 0.48 vol% GO nanocomposites, subjected to thermal annealing for various times. The pure polymer scatter is subtracted to leave the scattering from the GO network only. Red open circles: 10 minute samples, held in a hot press at 6 T and 160°C for 10 minutes. Blue open squares: 60 minute samples, held in a hot press at 6 T and 160°C for 60 minutes. Green open triangles: samples annealed at 190°C for 24 hours under vacuum (not pressed)

Figure 5 displays SAXS measurements of the PS + 0.48 vol% GO composite, treated in three different pressing and annealing regimes. Firstly, a set of samples (hereafter labeled ‘10 minute samples’) were pressed at 6 T and 160°C for 10 minutes, in order to achieve a minimal treatment whilst still producing a cohesive material. A second set of samples (‘60 minute samples’) were pressed at 6 T and 160°C for 60 minutes. A third set of samples (‘24 hours’) was annealed under vacuum at 190°C for 24 hours to produce fully melted samples that were allowed to flow into circular moulds under gravity.

The 10 minute samples (red circles in figure) show a power law close to the -4 exponent characteristic of scattering from smooth interfaces, which indicates the presence of well collapsed GO particles and/or aggregates at size ranges > 16 nm (shown at q values less than ~ 0.04 Å⁻¹). The intensity of the larger structures (in the low $-q$ power law region) increases by a factor of four with annealing from 10 to 60 minutes and a further factor of 2.5 from 60 minutes to 24 hours. This trend is entirely consistent with an increase in the aggregation of the GO. The large comparative change between 10 minutes and 60 minutes indicate that much of the structural changes occur in the first 60 minutes of annealing, with the caveat that the 24 hour samples were annealed at a higher temperature and in the absence of high pressure, and that these factors could be reasonably expected to affect the rate of any structural evolution.

The structural evolution observed in the SAXS measurements is also reflected by rheometry. Figure 6 shows the change in G' as a function of frequency at a temperature of 200°C for pure polystyrene (red), and nanocomposites with 0.48 vol% GO as pressed (blue) and after annealing for 24 hours at 200°C (green). While percolation is indicated by the increase at low frequency of G' for the as pressed sample, this disappears following annealing of the nanocomposite, where the frequency dependence of the sample closely matches that of the pure polystyrene. This shows that the percolated network of GO within the composite has been lost, and is evidence for aggregation of the GO. In addition a change is observed at the higher frequencies also. While the as pressed composite modulus is lower than that of

the pure PS, the annealed composite modulus increases to match that of the pure PS. The loss of this reduction is further evidence for a change in the dispersion of the GO within the nanocomposite.

Figure 6: Oscillatory rheology showing G' as a function of frequency at 200°C and 1% strain for pure PS and nanocomposites with 0.48 vol% GO. The effect of annealing on the composite was studied by annealing for 24 hours at 200°C under vacuum.

These results show that while there is indeed some interaction between the PS and the GO, the GO is not stable within the PS matrix. Processing of the polymer melt leads to aggregation of the GO within the nanocomposite and is therefore an important consideration in the preparation of polymer nanocomposites. It is clear that the GO does not form a thermodynamically stable dispersion within the PS, so further work should study an improved compatibilisation between the graphene and the PS, where any functionality on the graphene is also sufficiently stable to the thermal processing of the composite so as to maintain the dispersion over the processing time.

4 CONCLUSION

We have studied the dispersion and stability of polystyrene and graphene oxide nanocomposites, and have found that the GO aggregates within the composite during thermal processing. While rheometry has shown that a percolated network of GO is present at a concentration of 0.48 vol%, which also leads to a reduction in the plateau modulus, this is lost with annealing. SAXS shows aggregation of the GO within the composite. Our results highlight the importance of understanding and controlling the dispersion of fillers within a polymer matrix, which is vital for the end function of the composite, while also highlighting the thermodynamic instability of our system under melt conditions. This indicates that matrix specific functionalisations of the GO will be necessary to obtain a well dispersed stable composite.

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